

B.Sc.
Engg.
ME

Efficient Sulfur Removal from High Temperature Solid Oxide Fuel Cells Using Engineered Getter: A Comprehensive Computational Investigation

S.M. SALEHEEN OSMAN YEEAD (1710118)

MOHAMMAD TANVIR AZAD TAPU (1710059)

SUPERVISED BY:

Dr. MD. AMAN UDDIN

ASSISTANT PROFESSOR

BUET

BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

BANGLADESH UNIVERSITY OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY

MAY 2023

MAY
2023

Efficient Sulfur Removal from High Temperature Solid Oxide Fuel Cells Using Engineered Getter:
A Comprehensive Computational Investigation

**Efficient Sulfur Removal from High Temperature Solid Oxide
Fuel Cells Using Engineered Getter:
A Comprehensive Computational Investigation**

By

S.M. Saleheen Osman Yeead

(1710118)

Mohammad Tanvir Azad Tapu

(1710059)

**A thesis proffered for the degree of Bachelor of Science in
Mechanical Engineering**

BANGLADESH UNIVERSITY OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY

May 2023

Declaration of Authorship

We, namely S.M. Saleheen Osman Yeead and Mohammad Tanvir Azad Tapu, hereby assert that the research presented in this thesis entitled “Efficient Sulfur Removal From High Temperature Solid Oxide Fuel Cells Using Engineered Getters: A Comprehensive Computational Investigation” is original and entirely our own work. We confirm that this thesis, submitted for the attainment of the B.Sc. degree:

- Is composed solely by us.
- Is the product of our independent effort and has not been submitted for any other academic or professional qualification.
- We declare that the content of this thesis is our own except for explicitly referenced materials, and that it has not been submitted for any other academic or professional degree or qualification unless specifically stated.

Signed:

S,M. Saleheen Osman Yeead

Mohammad Tanvir Azad Tapu

Supervisor:

Dr. Md. Aman Uddin

Assistant Professor

Department of Mechanical Engineering, BUET

*This Thesis is Dedicated to Our Beloved Parents Who Always
Sacrifice Their Everything for Us*

Acknowledgements

We wish to express our sincere appreciation to the Department of Mechanical Engineering at Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (BUET) for their unwavering support and steadfast encouragement throughout the course of our research endeavors. We are deeply grateful to Dr. Md. Aman Uddin, Assistant Professor of Mechanical Engineering at BUET, for his sustained assistance in our thesis project, demonstrating remarkable patience, motivation, and extensive expertise, as well as providing us with cordial encouragement. In addition, we extend our heartfelt gratitude to our senior, whose invaluable assistance has contributed significantly to the completion of this thesis. We also wish to acknowledge the unwavering cooperation of our friends. Lastly, we would like to express our profound appreciation to our family members for their unwavering support and constant encouragement.

Abstract

The presence of airborne SO₂ contaminant irreversibly deteriorates the electrochemical activity of air electrodes in high-temperature electrochemical systems, such as solid oxide fuel cells. In this study, a computational model of a sulfur (S) getter has been developed to optimize the design of a 1 kW Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) system, effectively halting cathode degradation using the getter. A monolithic substrate with a cell density of 400 cells per square inch (cpsi) has been identified as the ideal material for the getter support. The coating thickness of the getter is 10 micrometers with a porosity of 50 percent. To determine the most effective getter, the performance of two popular getters, Strontium Nickel Oxide (SNO) and Strontium Manganese Oxide (SMO), were modeled under accelerated experimental conditions. The results demonstrate that SMO is superior to SNO in this application. Additionally, it has been found that a getter can last the entire lifespan of a SOFC plant under specific conditions.

Contents

Declaration of Authorship.....	1
Acknowledgements.....	3
Abstract.....	4
List of Figures.....	7
List of Tables.....	9
Nomenclature.....	10
Abbreviation.....	11
1.Introduction.....	12
1.1 Fuel Cell.....	12
1.1.1 Solid Oxide Fuel Cell.....	13
1.1.1.1 Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Components.....	16
1.2 Cathode Poisoning.....	17
1.3 Sulfur Dioxide.....	18
1.4 Getter.....	20
1.5 Present Work.....	20
1.6 Main Objectives of Present Work.....	20
1.7 Outline of Thesis.....	20
2. Literature Review.....	22
2.1 Methods to Reduce Cathode Poisoning.....	22
2.2 Method Without Getter.....	22
2.3 Getter.....	23
2.4 Use of Engineered Getter.....	23
2.4.1 Use and Computational Study of SNO to Capture Chromium.....	23
2.4.2. Use of SMO Getter.....	24
3. Mathematical Modeling.....	26
3.1 Physical Setup of Getter.....	26
3.2 Model Description and Assumptions.....	27
3.3 Governing Equations.....	28
3.4 Physical and Chemical Properties.....	31

3.5 Boundary Conditions.....	32
3.6 Numerical Method.....	32
3.7 User-defined Functions.....	32
3.8 User-defined Scalars.....	33
3.8 User-defined Memory.....	33
4. Results and Discussion.....	36
4.1 Reaction Mechanism between S and $Sr_xNi_yO_z$	36
4.2 Reaction Mechanism between S and $SrMnO_3$	36
4.3 Reaction Rate to Make Reaction Kinetically Limited.....	37
4.4 Theoretical Getter Surface Area Required for 1 kW SOFC System.....	38
4.5 SNO Getter for 1 kW SOFC.....	39
4.6 SMO Getter for 1 kW SOFC.....	48
4.7 Comparison of SMO and SNO Getter.....	54
4.8 Comparison of Chromium and Sulfur as Trace contaminant.....	57
4.9 Getter Useful Life.....	59
5. Conclusion and Recommendation.....	62
5.1 Conclusion.....	62
5.2 Recommendation.....	63
References.....	64

List of Figures

Figure 1.1: A typical fuel cell.....	12
Figure 1.2: Schematic of SOFC showing different components	13
Figure 1.3 SOFC schematic of a single cell between two interconnects, showing the passage of fuel and air streams relative to the electrodes	13
Figure 1.4 Schematic representation of SOFC cell geometries, including (l-r) planar, flat tubular, tubular, bell-and-spigot.....	14
Figure 1.5 Solid Oxide Fuel Cell stack for voltage amplification.....	15
Figure 1.6 Schematic representation of SOFC cell geometries, including (l-r) planar, flat tubular, tubular, bell-and-spigot (4)	15
Figure 1.7 impurity contaminations of SOFCs.....	16
Figure 1.8 Cathode poisoning in solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs)	17
Figure 1.9 (D) SO ₂ absorption on the Sr-terminated LSM particle surface, (E) SrSO ₄ island formation on the LSM surface leaving a Sr-deficient LSM, and (F) SO ₂ desorption and partial dissolution of SrSO ₄ onto LSM under SO ₂ -free air flow.....	19
Figure 2.1 Illustration of mechanism of SrCrO ₄ growth with time.....	23
Figure 2.2 Schematic representation of the S/Cr capturing mechanism of SMO getter: (a) Capturing process accompanied by the vertical growth of reaction compounds and the formation of the core-shell structure, and the proposed reaction mechanism for the absorption of (b) SO ₂ and (c) CrO ₂ (OH) ₂	23
Figure 3.1 Possible setup of getter for contaminant capture using SMO.....	25
Figure 3.2: Schematic Diagram of modeling Domain.....	26
Figure 3.3 Fabrication process of SMO honeycomb getter to purify the contaminated airstream.....	27
Figure 4.1 Theoretical getter surface area required for 1 kW SOFC system for 40000 hours operation.....	38
Figure 4.2 Sulfur concentration profile along center of the channel of SNO getter.....	39
Figure 4.3 Absorbed Sulfur profile in the SNO getter	40
Figure 4.4 Change in porosity of getter with time in SNO.....	43

Figure 4.5 Change in diffusivity of getter with time in SNO.....	46
Figure 4.6 S concentration profile along center of channel of SMO getter	48
Figure 4.7 Absorbed Sulfur profile in SMO getter	49
Figure 4.8 Change in porosity of SMO getter with time.....	51
Figure 4.9 Change of Sulfur Diffusivity with time in SMO.....	53
Figure 4.10 Absorbed Sulfur Profile in SMO and SNO Getter.....	54
Figure 4.11 Chromium concentration along center of channel in SNO and Sulfur concentration along center of channel in SNO.....	56
Figure 4.12 Absorbed contaminant profile of SNO getter for S and Cr separately.....	57
Figure 4.13 1-hour SO ₂ Design Value Trends Since 1990.....	58

List of Tables

Table 3.1. Model input parameters for gas and ceramic substrate properties.....	29
Table 3.2 Table Showing getter chemical properties.....	31
Table 3.3 Physical and Chemical properties of Sulfur and Chromium contaminant	31
Table 4.1 Area porosity table.....	37
Table 4.2 Sulfur outlet concentration for different flowtimes in SNO.....	38
Table 4.3 Sulfur Absorption for various flow time for SNO.....	40
Table 4.4 Change in Porosity with time in SNO.....	43
Table 4.5 Change in Diffusivity with time in SNO.....	45
Table 4.6 Sulfur outlet concentration for different flowtimes in SMO.....	47
Table 4.7 Sulfur Absorption for various flow time in SMO.....	48
Table 4.8 Change in Porosity with time in SMO.....	50
Table 4.9 Change in Sulfur Diffusivity with time in SMO.....	52
Figure 4.10 Comparison of porosity.....	54
Table 4.11 Comparison of diffusivity	55

Nomenclature

g	Gravitational acceleration	ms^{-2}
μ^{eff}	Effective viscosity	kg/m/s
$\delta(t)$	Thickness of product layer	m
C	Concentration	molm^{-3}
D	Diffusivity	m^2s^{-1}
ρ	Density	Kgm^{-3}
K	Reaction rate constant	μm
S	Sink	$\text{mol/m}^3/\text{s}$
A/V	Area to Volume Ratio	m^2/m^3

Abbreviation

- cpsi – cells per square inch
- SLPM – Standard Liter Per Minute
- CFD – Computational Fluid Dynamics
- BoP – Balance of Plant
- SOFC – Solid Oxide Fuel Cell
- SNO – Strontium Nickel Oxide
- SMO- Strontium Manganese Oxide
- EPA – Environmental Protection Agency
- MSDS – Material Safety Data Sheet
- UDF- User defined function
- UDS – User defined Scalar
- UDM – User Defined Memory
- LSM – Lanthanum Strontium Manganite
- YSZ -Yttria Stabilized Zirconia

Chapter 1

1. Introduction

1.1 Fuel Cell

A fuel cell is an electrochemical device that converts the chemical energy of a fuel directly into electrical energy, without combustion. It operates on the principle of an electrochemical reaction between a fuel, such as hydrogen, and an oxidant, such as oxygen, which generates electricity, water, and heat. Fuel cells offer several advantages over conventional power sources such as internal combustion engines or batteries.

One of the primary benefits of fuel cells is their high efficiency. They can convert up to 60% of the energy in a fuel into electricity, compared to only 20-25% for internal combustion engines. Fuel cells also can be a clean source of power, with water being the only significant byproduct. This makes them an attractive option for transportation, where they could help reduce greenhouse gas emissions and other air pollutants.

Fuel cells can also be used in stationary power applications, such as powering homes and businesses. They can provide reliable and continuous power, with little to no noise or emissions. In addition, fuel cells can be more efficient than traditional power plants, which often waste energy through the conversion of heat to electricity. There are several types of fuel cells, including proton exchange membrane (PEM), solid oxide (SOFC), molten carbonate (MCFC), and phosphoric acid (PAFC) fuel cells. Each type has its own advantages and disadvantages and is suited to different applications.

Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) are often considered to be superior to other fuel cells due to their high efficiency, fuel flexibility, and low emissions. Additionally, SOFCs have a longer lifespan and can operate at higher temperatures, which allows for more efficient and cost-effective power generation.

A fuel cell

is a device that converts chemical potential energy (energy stored in molecular bonds) into electrical energy.

SOURCE: Wikipedia Membrane electrode assembly

Figure 1.1: A typical fuel cell(1)

Overall, fuel cells have the potential to be a versatile and efficient source of power for a variety of applications. Ongoing research and development is focused on improving their performance, reducing costs, and expanding their use in different industries.

1.1.1 Solid Oxide Fuel Cell

A solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) is a type of fuel cell that operates at high temperatures (typically 800-1000°C) and uses a solid ceramic electrolyte. SOFCs can convert the chemical energy of a fuel, such as hydrogen or methane, directly into electrical energy with high efficiency, up to 60%. They have the potential to be a clean and efficient source of power for stationary and portable applications, such as homes, businesses, and vehicles. SOFCs can operate on a wide range of fuels, including renewable sources such as biogas and syngas from biomass gasification. Ongoing research and development are focused on improving the performance, durability, and cost-effectiveness of SOFCs, to make them more viable for widespread use.

In solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs), the current generation process involves the electrochemical reaction of oxygen ions and fuel (typically hydrogen or hydrocarbon) at the electrodes. At the anode, the fuel is oxidized to produce electrons and hydrogen ions. The electrons then flow through an external circuit, creating an electric current that can be used to power devices or recharge batteries. The hydrogen ions generated during this

process move through the solid oxide electrolyte and react with oxygen at the cathode, producing water and releasing electrons back into the circuit.

Figure 1.2: Schematic of SOFC showing different components (2)

This process is driven by the temperature difference between the anode and cathode sides of the fuel cell. At high temperatures (typically 800-1000°C), the ceramic electrolyte in SOFCs becomes conductive, allowing for the efficient transport of oxygen ions from the cathode to the anode. This high temperature operation also allows for the use of a variety of fuels, including renewable sources such as biogas and syngas from biomass gasification.

Figure 1.3 SOFC schematic of a single cell between two interconnects, showing the passage of fuel and air streams relative to the electrodes. (4)

Figure 1.4 Schematic representation of SOFC cell geometries, including (l— r) planar, flat tubular, tubular, bell-and-spigot (4)

Voltage amplification in solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) is achieved through the use of a stack of individual cells connected in series. Each cell in the stack generates a small voltage, typically around 0.7-1.0 volts, which is then added to the voltage of the previous cell in the series. This process continues until the desired output voltage is achieved. The voltage amplification is possible due to the internal electrochemical reactions that occur within each cell. The fuel and oxidant gases are fed into the cell, where they react to produce electricity and heat. The electricity is then conducted through the cell's electrodes and collected at the external circuit, while the heat is typically used for other purposes, such as steam generation. The stack design and the number of cells used can be customized to achieve the desired voltage output and power generation capacity. Additionally, various materials and manufacturing techniques can be used to optimize the performance and efficiency of the SOFC stack.

Figure 1.5 Solid Oxide Fuel Cell stack for voltage amplification (3)

1.1.1.1 SOFC Components

Anode is Nickel zirconia cermet.

Solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) cathodes are often referred to as "air cathodes" because they typically use atmospheric air as the source of oxygen for the electrochemical reaction that occurs within the fuel cell.

At the cathode, oxygen from the air reacts with the electrons and hydrogen ions that have traveled through the external circuit from the anode. This reaction creates negatively charged oxygen ions that move through the solid oxide electrolyte to the anode, where they react with the fuel to create water and release more electrons.

The use of atmospheric air as the source of oxygen in SOFC cathodes has several advantages, including the fact that it eliminates the need for expensive and complex oxygen separation systems. However, the use of air cathodes can also present challenges related to the presence of impurities and the potential for chemical reactions that can degrade the performance of the fuel cell over time. As a result, ongoing research in SOFCs is focused on developing new cathode materials and designs that can improve efficiency, durability, and reliability.

Figure 1.6 Schematic representation of SOFC cell geometries, including (l— r) planar, flat tubular, tubular, bell-and-spigot (4)

Most popular air cathode is LSM ($\text{La}_{1-2x}\text{Sr}_x\text{MnO}_{3\pm\delta}$) for SOFC. LSM stands for lanthanum strontium manganite. It is the electrode chosen for our study.

The LSM material is particularly well-suited for use in SOFCs because it is a good conductor of electrons and can catalyze the electrochemical reaction that occurs at the cathode. In addition, LSM is relatively stable at the high temperatures (typically 800-1000°C) required for SOFC operation, and it is relatively inexpensive compared to some other cathode materials.

In an SOFC, the LSM cathode is typically applied as a thin layer onto a porous ceramic structure. When oxygen from the air comes into contact with the LSM cathode, it reacts with the electrons and positively charged oxygen ions (produced at the anode) to create negatively charged oxygen ions. These ions then move through the solid oxide electrolyte to the anode, where they react with fuel to create water and release more electrons. The flow of electrons through an external circuit creates a direct current (DC) electrical output that can be used to power devices or recharge batteries.

Yttria-stabilized zirconia is the electrolyte typically when LSM is used. (4)

SOFC Components are subjected to various type of impurity contaminations. In figure 1.7 the contaminations of different components are shown.

Figure 1.7 impurity contaminations of SOFCs (4)

1.2 Cathode Poisoning

Figure 1.8 Cathode poisoning in solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) (27)

Cathode poisoning in solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) refers to the gradual degradation of the cathode material due to the accumulation of impurities that come from the air stream used to provide oxygen to the fuel cell.

Impurities such as sulfur compounds, carbon dioxide, and water vapor can react with the cathode material and form unwanted compounds that can reduce the activity of the cathode and impair its ability to catalyze the electrochemical reaction that occurs within the fuel cell. Over time, this can lead to a decrease in the fuel cell's efficiency and performance. (5)

1.3 Sulfur Dioxide

Sulfur dioxide (SO_2) is a gaseous air pollutant that poses significant challenges to the performance and durability of air cathodes in Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs). SO_2 is primarily emitted from the combustion of fossil fuels, such as coal and oil, as well as industrial processes. Understanding the detrimental effects of SO_2 on SOFC air cathodes is crucial for developing strategies to mitigate its impact and optimize the efficiency and longevity of SOFC systems.

When SO_2 is present in the air, it can have a profound influence on the electrochemical activity of air cathodes within the SOFC. The detrimental effects of SO_2 stem from its ability to adsorb onto the cathode surface and hinder the oxygen reduction reactions. These oxygen reduction reactions are fundamental to the operation of the SOFC, as they facilitate the conversion of chemical energy to electrical energy. When SO_2 molecules adsorb onto the cathode surface, they create a barrier that restricts the access of oxygen to

the electrode surface, thus impeding the oxygen reduction reactions. Consequently, this interference leads to reduced cell efficiency and power output.

Moreover, SO_2 can instigate chemical reactions within the cathode material, giving rise to the formation of sulfates or other sulfur-containing compounds. These compounds can accumulate within the cathode structure and contribute to the blockage of the cathode pores. This obstructs the flow of oxygen to the electrode surface, further diminishing the cathode's performance. The blockage of the cathode pores not only restricts oxygen diffusion but also hampers the removal of reaction by-products, thus exacerbating the deterioration of the cathode.

Furthermore, the presence of sulfur species within the cathode material can stimulate solid-state reactions, such as sulfation (Figure 1.8). Sulfation involves the reaction of sulfur species with perovskite materials commonly used in SOFC cathodes, resulting in the formation of sulfate compounds. These sulfate compounds can alter the crystal structure of the cathode material, impairing its electrochemical activity and overall performance. The sulfation process is particularly detrimental as it irreversibly damages the cathode material, leading to its progressive degradation and loss of functionality.

To address the challenges posed by SO_2 , various strategies have been developed to mitigate its detrimental effects on SOFC air cathodes.

Although the concentration of sulfur dioxide is very low in air (75 ppb for hourly primary standard), the long-term exposure of electrode to air flow leads to air contaminant accumulation. This degrades the cathodic activity for oxygen reduction. (18,19) The degradation caused by sulfur dioxide is slow but continuous and severe in long term.

Figure 1.9 (D) SO₂ absorption on the Sr-terminated LSM particle surface, (E) SrSO₄ island formation on the LSM surface leaving a Sr-deficient LSM, and (F) SO₂ desorption and partial dissolution of SrSO₄ onto LSM under SO₂-free air flow. (26)

1.4 Getter

A getter in a solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) is a material that is added to the fuel cell to help remove unwanted impurities from the fuel and air streams. The term "getter" refers to the fact that this material "gets" or absorbs impurities, much like a sponge absorbs water.

The use of getters is an important strategy for improving the performance and durability of SOFCs, particularly in applications where the fuel and air streams may contain high levels of impurities. However, the use of getters must be carefully optimized to avoid introducing other problems, such as corrosion or reduced conductivity, into the fuel cell system. Getters are fabricated from non-noble and non-strategic ceramic constituents and supported on conventional porous ceramic support. (7,8)

1.5 Present Work

The current work consists of performance of two types of getters. Their performances are analyzed individually and a comparison of their performance is also completed.

1.6 Main Objectives of Present work

- Design an engineered getter to capture the intrinsic Sulfur contaminant available in air based on previous technology
- Analyze and perform a comparative study between the two getters comparatively
- Design and optimize engineered getter that displays robust stability at high temperature and humid environments without phase transformation and hydrolysis
- Find the lifetime of the getter

1.7 Outline of the Thesis

There are six chapters in this dissertation. This chapter begins with a brief introduction that includes the goal and objective.

Chapter 2 comprises reviews of previous research literature.

Chapter 3 presents the current study's mathematical modeling. In addition, the governing equations, geometry, and boundary conditions are also depicted.

Chapter 4 covers the present study's findings and discussion.

Chapter 5 includes conclusions and recommendations for further research on the current thesis.

Chapter 2

2. Literature Review

Due to their high conversion efficiencies, fuel flexibility, and low emissions, solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) are a desirable technology for the generation of clean and efficient electricity. However, because SOFCs are susceptible to several poisons, their performance may suffer and their cell lifetime may be shortened. Sulfur and chromium poisoning are two typical forms of toxicity that can happen in SOFCs.

The airborne sulfur and chromium reacts with cathode material (Lanthanum strontium manganese) which degrades the cathode which eventually reduce the lifetime of the solid oxide fuel cell according with disrupting its spontaneous operation.

2.1 Methods to Reduce Cathode Poisoning

- Developing contaminant-tolerant cathode materials (e.g., $\text{La}(\text{Ni}, \text{Fe})\text{O}_3$ and Nd_2NiO_4) (20,21)
- Cathode surface modification
 - oxidation-resistant alloys (e.g., ZMGTM232 series from Hitachi Metals) (22)
 - surface coating of metallic components (e.g., $\text{Mn}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ spinel) (23)
- Use of getter

2.2 Without Getter

Among all of this method first two methods have several limitations. The first two methods have issues under high temperature operating conditions owing to thermal expansion discrepancy and chemical incompatibility between adjacent materials.

Such as –

- Interdiffusion
- Crack Propagation
- Spallation

These hinder the long-term efficacy of cathode. (24,25)

2.3 Getter

In fuel cell technology, a getter is a specialized material or device that is used to actively remove or "get" impurities, particularly gases, from the fuel cell environment to maintain high purity and stable operation.

Getters are typically used in fuel cells that operate at high temperatures, such as solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) and proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs), where the presence of impurities can adversely affect performance and durability

Getters work by adsorbing or absorbing impurities from the fuel cell environment, effectively trapping them and preventing them from interfering with the electrochemical processes that occur within the fuel cell. Adsorption is the process by which impurities adhere to the surface of the getter material, while absorption is the process by which impurities are taken up and retained within the bulk of the getter material.

The choice of getter material and its specific properties, such as surface area, pore size, and chemical affinity, are carefully designed to selectively target and capture specific impurities, such as moisture, oxygen, carbon monoxide, or sulfur-containing compounds.

Getters play a critical role in ensuring the long-term performance and durability of fuel cells by maintaining a clean and controlled fuel cell environment.

2.4 Use of Engineered Getter

Two getters, SMO and SNO is modeled, observed and reported for sulfur removal.

2.4.1 Use and Computational Study of SNO to capture Chromium

$\text{Sr}_9\text{Ni}_7\text{O}_{21}$ was used as getter to capture endogenous Cr contaminants that is generated due to high temperature operation due to (5)

- chromia scales grown on metallic components
- Balance-of-Plant (BoP)

Figure 2.1 Illustration of mechanism of SrCrO₄ growth with time (5)

2.4.2 Use of SMO getter

Strontium manganese oxide (SMO) is found to be a robust getter for co-capture of airborne Cr and S contaminants. Investigations found that both Sr and Mn cations contribute to absorption reaction. SMO getter also displays robust stability at high temperature and in humid environments without phase transformation and hydrolysis. These results demonstrate the feasibility of the use of SMO getter under operating conditions representative of high-temperature electrochemical systems.

Figure 2.2 Schematic representation of the S/Cr capturing mechanism of SMO getter:
(a) Capturing process accompanied by the vertical growth of reaction compounds and the formation of the core-shell structure, and the proposed reaction mechanism for the absorption of (b) SO_2 and (c) $\text{CrO}_2(\text{OH})_2$ (6)

Chapter 3

3. Mathematical Modeling

The primary step in investigating any numerical problem involves creating a simplified model of the system. Once the model is established, the next step is to develop a mathematical model that may use one or more algebraic, differential, or integral equations. The subsequent phase involves solving these equations using appropriate computational methods and identifying the relevant initial and boundary conditions based on the physical problem. Therefore, mathematical modeling is critical to obtain the most precise and realistic solution for a physical problem. Although a simplified schematic model may aid in easier calculation, a more intricate model that incorporates more variables can yield a more accurate solution. Therefore, it is crucial to balance the model's simplicity with the required solution accuracy.

3.1 Physical Setup of Getter

Physical setup of getter is outside the scope of this thesis due to the lack of resources and facilities. A physical Setup is shown in the following figure:

Figure 3.1 Possible setup of getter for contaminant capture using SMO (6)

3.2 Model Description and Assumptions

Monolithic substrate structure with 400 cpsi (cells per square inch), as shown in Figure 3.2, is selected as the getter support due to its large open front area and straight parallel channels which ensure low flow resistance. (5) The model comprises of half of a flow channel with wall of the channel coated with $\text{Sr}_x\text{Ni}_y\text{O}_z$ material to capture Cr. The following assumptions are made in the model:

- Transient and two-dimensional model;
- Steady state and isothermal conditions;
- Ideal gas mixtures;
- Modeling domain is symmetric;
- Getter coating is $10\mu\text{m}$ thick and 50% porous;
- Reaction product occupies open pores;
- No slip condition at the wall;
- Incompressible and laminar flow;

Figure 3.2: Schematic Diagram of modeling Domain (5)

Figure 3.3 Fabrication process of SMO honeycomb getter to purify the contaminated airstream (6)

3.3 Governing Equations

The governing equations include conservation of mass, momentum, and species:

Mass

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad [1]$$

Momentum

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\mu}^{\text{eff}} \nabla \mathbf{u}) + \rho \mathbf{g} \quad [2]$$

Sulfur (gas phase)

$$\frac{\partial(C_S)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} C_S) = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{D} \nabla C_S) + S \quad [3]$$

where ρ is density (kg/m^3); $\mathbf{u}$ is the velocity (m/s); t is the time (s); p is the pressure (Pa); $\boldsymbol{\mu}^{\text{eff}}$ is the effective viscosity ($\text{kg/m}\cdot\text{s}$); $\mathbf{g}$ is the gravitational acceleration (m^2/s); C_S is the molar concentration of Sulfur (mol/m^3); and S is the sink term corresponding to the Sulfur capture rate ($\text{mol/m}^3/\text{s}$).

The source term in species conservation equation depends on the reaction rate, and the reaction process for the interaction of SO_2 and getter material. Reaction schemes can be controlled by kinetics and solid-state diffusion of Sulfur (inward diffusion) or

Strontium (Sr) (outward diffusion) in the reaction product layer.

If the reaction process is kinetically limited, kinetics is considered to be the rate limiting (slow) compared to S diffusion through the gas film and through the pore present in the coating. Considering first order reaction rate between S and Sr or Strontium Oxide, sink term in species conservation equation is given by

$$S_k = k \times C_S \times \left(\frac{A}{V}\right)_g \quad [4]$$

where, C_S is the concentration of S(mol/m³); k is reaction rate (m/s) and $(A/V)_g$ is the area to volume ratio of getter (m²/m³).

Reaction rate (k) of S and getter material in equation 4 can be calculated based on the results of transpiration testing using following equation

$$C_S * k * A_{ag} = n'_S \quad [5]$$

where, n'_S is rate of S capture (mol/s) and A_{ag} is active surface area of getter (m²), and these values can be calculated using following equations

$$n'_S = \frac{P_S \times Q}{R \times T} \quad [6]$$

$$A_{ag} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{\pi D_g^2}{4} \times L_{ag} \right) \times \left(\frac{A}{V} \right)_s \right) \times t_{coat} \times \epsilon_{coat} \right) \times A_{coat} \quad [7]$$

where P_S partial pressure of S in air, (Pa); Q is air flow rate in transpiration test, (m³/s); R is molar gas constant (m² kg/ s²/K/mol); T is temperature (K); L_{ag} is the active length of getter (m); $(A/V)_s$ = area to volume ratio of getter support (m²/m³).

Table 3.1. Model input parameters for gas and ceramic substrate properties

Description	Value	Reference
Number of channels in getter	400	
Channel length, mm	50	
Air flow rate, SLPM	4	
Channel width, mm	1	

Description	Value	Reference
Temperature, °C	850	
Solid phase Sr diffusivity,	1×10^{-8}	9
Air density at 850oC, kg/m3	0.3139	
Gas phase SO2 Diffusivity, m2/s	1.385×10^{-4}	10
Getter Material	SrMnO ₃ , Sr ₉ Ni ₇ O ₂₁	
Molecular Volume of NiO, cm3/mol	11.2	5
Molecular Volume of Mn ₂ O ₃ , cm ³ /mol	35.8	11,12
Coating Thickness, μm	10	
Surface area of coating, m ² /g	10	
Porosity of coating	0.5	

If the reaction process is solid state diffusion limited, solid state diffusion of cations through the product layer is rate limiting (slowest step) and gaseous diffusion through the gas phase and through the pore is very fast. At the beginning of the reaction, product layer thickness is considered to be zero, so overall reaction is limited by chemical kinetics. As time progresses, the thickness of the product layer increases and the reaction product thickness buildup will be dominated by the diffusion of cations through product layer. Considering solid state diffusion is rate limiting, sink term in species conservation equation is given by (5)

$$S_d = D_{sr} \times \frac{C_{sr}}{\delta} \times \left(\frac{A}{V}\right)_g \quad [8]$$

where, C_{sr} is the concentration of Sr (mol/m³), D_{sr} is the diffusion coefficient of Sr through product layer (m²/s) and δ is the thickness of product layer (m). In equation 8, it is assumed

that Sr will diffuse through the product layer and react with S species because diffusivity of Sr in metal oxide (9) is reported to be higher than that of S.

Solid state diffusion of Sr is much slower compared to gas phase diffusion of S. Hence S capture rate will be much slower in solid state diffusion case compared to kinetically limited case. To increase S capture rate and full utilization of getter material, reaction processes must remain kinetically limited throughout the getter life. One way to make the reaction kinetically limited is to make smaller particle of getter material so that the getter will be used up before the reaction process becomes solid state diffusion limited. Reaction will remain kinetically limited until $S_d \geq S_k$. So from equation 4 and 8

$$\delta \leq \frac{D_{sr} \times C_{sr}}{k \times C_S} \quad [9]$$

3.4 Physical and Chemical Properties

Table 3.2 Table Showing getter chemical properties (13)

Description	SNO	SMO
Density, kg/m ³	5406	5460
Molecular Weight, kg/mol	1.53542	0.19056
Molecular Volume, cm ³ /mol	284	34.90

Table 3.3 Physical and Chemical properties of Sulfur and Chromium contaminant (14,15)

Descriptions	Value
Gas phase Cr diffusivity, m ² /s	1.08775 × 10 ⁻⁴
Solid phase Cr diffusivity, m ² /s	1 × 10 ⁻¹⁹
Molecular volume of SrCrO4, cm ³ /mol	52.2
Gas phase SO2 diffusivity, m ² /s	1.385 × 10 ⁻⁴
Solid phase S diffusivity, m ² /s	1 × 10 ⁻¹⁹
Molecular volume of SrSO4, cm ³ /mol	46.38

3.5 Boundary Conditions

At the inlet of the channel, concentration and velocity of the air flow is specified and the outlet is specified with typical pressure outlet boundary conditions. The wall is treated as impermeable with a no slip condition and center of the channel is set to symmetry boundary condition.

At inlet, concentration = 1.071×10^{-5} mol/m³

Velocity at inlet = 0.6855 m/s

3.6 Numerical Method

The differential equations were discretized using the finite volume method, whereby a first-order upwind scheme was employed to evaluate the convective-diffusive flux through each computational cell. These discretized equations were subsequently constructed using the finite volume method and solved within the ANSYS-Fluent commercial computational fluid dynamics software, which was customized through user-defined functions.

3.7 User-defined Functions

ANSYS Fluent is a powerful computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software that offers advanced simulation capabilities for fluid flow and other complex physical phenomena. One of the key features that sets ANSYS Fluent apart from other CFD software is the ability to customize its functionality using user-defined functions (UDFs).UDFs are pieces of code that are written in programming languages such as C or C++, and they allow users to extend the functionality of ANSYS Fluent beyond its built-in capabilities. Users can define their own boundary conditions, source terms, and material properties using UDFs, making it possible to model more complex physical systems and phenomena. UDFs can be used in different parts of the simulation process, including initialization, boundary conditions, and post-processing. They can be called at different stages of the simulation and can have different levels of complexity, from simple functions to complex algorithms. One of the most common uses of UDFs in ANSYS Fluent is to define custom boundary conditions. For example, a UDF can be used to specify a temperature or velocity profile at the inlet of a pipe or the boundary of a fluid domain. This allows users to model

more complex geometries and boundary conditions that cannot be easily defined using ANSYS Fluent's built-in boundary conditions. Another common use of UDFs is to define custom source terms, such as chemical reactions or heat transfer. These UDFs can be used to model more complex physical phenomena, such as combustion or multiphase flows. UDFs can also be used to customize the post-processing capabilities of ANSYS Fluent. For example, a UDF can be used to define a custom output file format or to extract additional data from the simulation results.

Overall, the use of UDFs in ANSYS Fluent provides users with a powerful tool for customizing and extending the software's functionality to meet their specific needs. By enabling the modeling of more complex physical systems and phenomena, UDFs help to push the boundaries of what is possible with computational fluid dynamics.

DEFINE_ADJUST, DEFINE_SOURCE, DEFINE_EXECUTE_AT_END,
DEFINE_DIFFUSIVITY – have been used. (16)

3.8 User Defined Scalars (UDS)

User-defined scalars (UDS) are additional variables that can be defined in ANSYS Fluent to capture information beyond what is already computed by the solver. UDS can be used to track additional quantities of interest, such as species concentration, chemical reaction progress, or heat release rate. UDS are defined using user-defined functions (UDFs), which are pieces of code written in programming languages such as C or C++. These UDFs are integrated into ANSYS Fluent's solver loop, allowing the UDS to be solved along with the other governing equations of the fluid flow or other physical phenomena being modeled. Once a UDS has been defined, it can be used to compute additional quantities of interest that are not directly available from ANSYS Fluent's built-in variables. For example, a UDS that tracks the concentration of a particular species can be used to compute the reaction rate of that species, or to estimate the formation of combustion products. UDS can also be used to model more complex physical phenomena, such as multiphase flows or reacting flows. For example, a UDS that tracks the mass fraction of a specific chemical species in a mixture can be used to model the transport and reactions of that species in a combustion process.

The use of UDS in ANSYS Fluent provides users with a powerful tool for capturing additional information beyond what is already computed by the solver. By defining UDS, users can tailor their simulations to meet their specific needs, making it possible to model more complex physical systems and phenomena. UDS can be visualized and analyzed in ANSYS Fluent using the software's post-processing capabilities. For example, contour plots can be generated to show the distribution of a UDS throughout the computational domain, or line plots can be used to show the temporal evolution of a UDS over time.

Overall, the use of UDS in ANSYS Fluent provides users with a powerful tool for customizing and extending the software's functionality to meet their specific needs. By enabling the modeling of more complex physical systems and phenomena, UDS help to push the boundaries of what is possible with computational fluid dynamics. In this thesis, one user defined scalar is used.

3.9 User Defined Memory (UDM)

User-defined memory (UDM) is a feature in ANSYS Fluent that allows users to define and store additional data within the solver. UDM is a flexible tool that can be used to store a variety of information, including scalar or vector fields, material properties, boundary conditions, and other quantities of interest that are not directly available from ANSYS Fluent's built-in variables. UDM is defined using user-defined functions (UDFs), which are pieces of code written in programming languages such as C or C++. These UDFs are integrated into ANSYS Fluent's solver loop, allowing the UDM to be updated and modified throughout the simulation. Once a UDM has been defined, it can be used to capture additional information that is not directly computed by ANSYS Fluent. For example, a UDM can be used to store additional boundary conditions that are not available in the software's built-in boundary condition library. This can be useful in cases where the flow or other physical phenomena being modeled are complex and require customized boundary conditions to accurately capture the behavior of the system. UDM can also be used to store additional data that is needed for post-processing and analysis. For example, a UDM can be used to store the results of a custom calculation or analysis

that is performed during the simulation. This data can then be used to generate custom plots and visualizations in ANSYS Fluent's post-processing environment.

The use of UDM in ANSYS Fluent provides users with a powerful tool for customizing and extending the software's functionality to meet their specific needs. By defining and storing additional data within the solver, users can tailor their simulations to capture the specific behavior of the system being modeled. UDM can be visualized and analyzed in ANSYS Fluent using the software's post-processing capabilities. For example, contour plots can be generated to show the distribution of a UDM throughout the computational domain, or line plots can be used to show the temporal evolution of a UDM over time.

Overall, the use of UDM in ANSYS Fluent provides users with a powerful tool for capturing and storing additional data within the solver. By enabling the modeling of more complex physical systems and phenomena, UDM help to push the boundaries of what is possible with computational fluid dynamics. In this thesis, 3 user defined memory was used.

Chapter 4

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Reaction Mechanism between S and $\text{Sr}_x\text{Ni}_y\text{O}_z$

The possible reaction between dominant phase in getter ($\text{Sr}_9\text{Ni}_7\text{O}_{21}$) and dominant phase in SO_2 is shown in Eq. 10. There can be various steps in reaction path, but 1 mole of $\text{Sr}_9\text{Ni}_7\text{O}_{21}$ can produce 9 moles of SrSO_4 and 7 moles of NiO . The total volume of solid products (9 mole of SrSO_4 and 7 moles of NiO) is 495.82 cm^3 and the volume of solid reactant (1 mole of $\text{Sr}_9\text{Ni}_7\text{O}_{21}$) is 284 cm^3 as calculated from the molecular volume provided in Table 3.1,3.2 and 3.3. So, the volume of solid product is almost two times higher than the volume of solid reactants.

The surface layer initially grows rapidly and then slows down after 200 hours possibly due to formation of dense product layer. The crystalline particles also increase in size with time due to diffusion of Sr through the dense layer and continued reaction with S. The overall interaction of S with the $\text{Sr}_x\text{Ni}_y\text{O}_z$ getter surface is schematically shown in Figure 2.1.

Preferential reaction of SO_2 with the getter leads to the formation of a thin layer of SrSO_4 that grows with time. Preferential utilization of Sr from the getter is considered to lead to the rejection and formation of a separate NiO phase. Size of the SrSO_4 particles gradually increase and NiO segregates from $\text{Sr}_x\text{Ni}_y\text{O}_z$ and deposits in the inner layer. Based on the results it can be postulated that the reaction processes between S and $\text{Sr}_x\text{Ni}_y\text{O}_z$ getter initially remain kinetically limited, however, when product layers form, the reaction processes become solid state diffusion limited.

4.2 Reaction Mechanism between S and SrMnO_3

The possible reaction between dominant phase in getter (SrMnO₃) and dominant phase in SO₂ is shown in Eq. 11. There can be various steps in reaction path, but 1 mole of SrMnO₃ can produce 1 mole of SrSO₄ and 0.5 mole of Mn₂O₃. (6) The total volume of solid products (1 mole of SrSO₄ and 0.5 mole of Mn₂O₃) is 64.28 cm³ and the volume of solid reactant (1 mole of SrMnO₃) is 34.9 cm³ as calculated from the molecular volume provided in Table 3.1,3.2 and 3.3. So, the volume of solid product is almost two times higher than the volume of solid reactants.

The overall interaction of S with the SrMnO₃ getter surface is schematically shown in Figure 2.2. Preferential reaction of SO₂ with the getter leads to the formation of a thin layer of SrSO₄ that grows with time. Preferential utilization of Sr from the getter is considered to lead to the rejection and formation of a separate Mn₂O₃ phase. Size of the SrSO₄ particles gradually increase and Mn₂O₃ segregates from SrMnO₃ and deposits in the inner layer. Based on the results it can be postulated that the reaction processes between S and SrMnO₃ getter initially remain kinetically limited, however, when product layers form, the reaction processes become solid state diffusion limited.

4.3 Reaction Rate and particle size to make reaction kinetically limited

Using Equation 5, and with reference to Table 3.1, for the specified flowrate and temperature, as well as the coating thickness, porosity, and other relevant parameters pertaining to SNO, it is found that -

$$\text{Reaction rate} = 4.79 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m/s}$$

$$\text{Thickness of product layer} = 0.686 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$$

Using Equation 5, and with reference to Table 3.1, for the specified flowrate and temperature, as well as the coating thickness, porosity, and other relevant parameters pertaining to SMO, it is found that -

$$\text{Reaction rate} = 4.74 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m/s}$$

$$\text{Thickness of product layer} = 0.693 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$$

4.4 Theoretical getter surface area required for 1 kW SOFC system

For a 1 kW SOFC system for 40,000 hours of operation amount of getter material required to capture all the S is calculated based on chemical reaction Eq. 10. Since the volume of solid reaction products is almost two times higher than the volume of solid reactants according to equation 10, the porosity of getter coating must be 50% or higher for increased utilization of getter. Considering the required getter material is coated on a substrate with a certain thickness and porosity, getter surface area required (theoretical) to capture all the S is calculated and presented in Figure 4.2. With the increase of coating porosity and decrease of coating thickness, required getter surface area increases.

Table 4.1 Area porosity Table

Thickness, μm	Thickness, cm	porosity	Area
10	0.001	0.5	244.4359264
10	0.001	0.6	305.5449079
10	0.001	0.7	407.3932106
10	0.001	0.8	611.0898159
10	0.001	0.9	1222.179632

Figure 4.1 Theoretical getter surface area required for 1 kW SOFC system for 40000 hours operation. (5)

4.5 SNO Getter for 1 kW SOFC

Solving the model for 40,000 - 50000 hours duration is computationally impractical. If the getter life mainly depends on the total dosage of S and not on inlet concentration, the getter can be designed for a higher S concentration and the design can still be applied for lower S concentration for longer duration. This is called accelerated modeling. This concept has been used in this comprehensive computational study.

Some of the results generated from simulation will now be examined. The inlet concentration is $1.071 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol/m}^3$. Air flow rate 4 SLPM and temperature 850°C . Coating thickness $10 \mu\text{m}$ and coating porosity 50%. The following table can be found from figure 4.2 by comprehensive careful observation –

Table 4.2 Sulfur outlet concentration for different flowtimes

Flowtime (hours)	Sulfur outlet concentration (mol/m ³)
28	1.629×10^{-11}
56	3.53×10^{-11}

Flowtime (hours)	Sulfur outlet concentration (mol/m ³)
76	6.14×10^{-11}
200	9.23×10^{-10}
300	4.66×10^{-9}
400	1.74×10^{-8}
500	5.29×10^{-8}

Figure 4.2 Sulfur concentration profile along center of the channel of the getter

From the above graph it is clear that the concentration at outlet is increasing with increasing time. This indicates that the getter is losing this capability to remove impurity and provide. Getter outlet concentration has to be less than 10^{-9} mol/m³ for getter to be used under

accelerated conditions. However, accelerated the model has a factor of 263.5. So, in real life conditions, this getter can be used for 52000 hours with a factor of safety equal to 1. The capacity of the getter will now be examined. The following results is presented in the form of a table from figure 4.13–

Table 4.3 Sulfur Absorption for various flow time for SNO

Flowtime (hours)	Maxed out Sulfur Capacity (%)	Length up to (mm)
28	-	-
56	64	4
76	64	6
200	64	17
300	64	24
400	64	29
500	64	34

Figure 4.3 Absorbed Sulfur profile in the getter

The figure from 4.3 shows the absorbed Sulfur profile in terms of Sulfur capacity (ratio of total sulfur absorbed to maximum sulfur absorption capacity) of the getter. Amount of S captured in the getter increases with time, and S front moves forward before reaching maximum capacity. More than 35% of getter remains unused as S front advances. Although absorbed S profile becomes flat at 64% capacity, it keeps absorbing S albeit in a slow rate.

Figure 4.4 shows the porosity results for SNO getter for 7 different flow time. Porosity refers to the presence of void spaces or empty regions within a material. In the specific context of a getter, porosity represents the proportion of empty volume relative to the total volume of the material. Porosity plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of a getter as it directly influences important characteristics such as surface area, gas permeability, and adsorption capacity.

Porosity is of utmost importance for a getter due to its direct impact on the ability of the material to adsorb or absorb gases and impurities from the surrounding environment. A higher porosity translates to a larger surface area available for gas-surface interactions, enabling a greater number of gas molecules to come into contact with the getter material. This results in an increased adsorption capacity and enhances the getter's ability to capture and remove contaminants. Additionally, higher porosity also facilitates better gas permeability, allowing the gas to diffuse more easily into the getter material and reach the active sites for adsorption.

However, it is crucial to strike a balance when determining the porosity of a getter since excessive porosity can compromise the material's mechanical strength and overall stability. It is necessary to optimize the porosity-mechanical property relationship to ensure the getter can withstand the operating conditions of the system without undergoing structural degradation.

In the realm of Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs), getter materials are commonly employed to eliminate impurities, particularly sulfur compounds, from the air that enters the cathode region. These getter materials are typically applied as a coating or integrated

within the support structure of the cathode. The porosity of the getter material plays a pivotal role in determining its performance within the SOFC system.

The implementation of getter porosity in SOFCs involves meticulous design considerations and specific fabrication techniques. One approach is to utilize a monolithic substrate with high porosity, such as a highly porous ceramic material or a foam structure, as the supporting medium for the getter. The open-cell structure of the substrate establishes a network of interconnected pores that facilitate efficient gas flow and enable access to the getter material.

Another method focuses on controlling the porosity of the getter coating itself. This can be accomplished through various techniques, including precise adjustment of deposition parameters during the coating process, incorporation of pore-forming agents, or utilization of materials with inherent porosity. By actively regulating the porosity, the surface area available for gas adsorption can be optimized, ensuring effective removal of contaminants from the cathode region.

Furthermore, advancements in fabrication technologies, such as additive manufacturing or template-assisted methods, offer promising avenues for tailoring the porosity of getter materials with remarkable precision. These techniques enable the creation of intricate geometries and controlled porosity distributions, thereby enhancing the performance and customization of getters to meet the specific requirements of different applications.

In summary, porosity assumes a critical role in the performance of getter materials within SOFCs due to its direct influence on gas adsorption capacity and permeability. Careful control of porosity is essential to strike a balance between enhanced adsorption capability and mechanical stability. Implementing getter porosity in SOFCs entails utilizing porous substrates or manipulating the porosity of getter coatings through various fabrication techniques. Optimizing getter porosity contributes to the efficient removal of impurities, particularly sulfur compounds, from the cathode region, consequently improving the overall performance and lifespan of SOFC systems.

From Figure 4.4, the following table is generated.

Table 4.4 Change in Porosity with time in SNO

Flow time (hours)	Maximum porosity reached in channel length (mm)
28	18
56	20
76	23
200	33
300	41
400	50
500	50

Figure 4.4 Change in porosity of getter with time in SNO

Figures 4.4 shows the change in average porosity of getter coating with time. The porosity of the getter decreases with time due to formation of dense solid products in the pores.

Lower porosity decreases transport of Sulfur to the reaction sites and decreases Sulfur absorption and Sulfur front advances before reaching to the maximum capacity of the getter as shown in the figures. So, getter needs to be highly porous for higher utilization of getter.

Figure 4.5 shows the diffusivity change of sulfur gas contaminant with time. Diffusivity refers to the ability of a substance to diffuse or spread through a medium. It is a fundamental property that characterizes the rate at which molecules or particles move and disperse within a given material or environment. In the context of gaseous contaminants and getters in Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs), diffusivity plays a crucial role in determining the efficiency of contaminant capture and removal.

The diffusivity of a gaseous contaminant is of paramount importance for getters in SOFCs due to its direct impact on the transport and distribution of the contaminant within the system. Understanding and controlling the diffusivity of gaseous contaminants is essential for achieving effective contaminant capture and maintaining the performance and durability of SOFCs.

One key aspect is the rate at which the contaminant diffuses towards the getter material. Higher diffusivity enables faster movement of the contaminant molecules, allowing them to reach the getter surface more rapidly. This is particularly important in SOFCs, as a rapid and efficient capture of contaminants is vital to prevent their accumulation and detrimental effects on the cathode region.

Moreover, the diffusivity of the gaseous contaminant affects the extent of its penetration into the getter material. A higher diffusivity enables the contaminant to diffuse deeper into the getter structure, maximizing the utilization of the getter material's adsorption capacity. This is crucial in SOFCs to ensure that the contaminants are effectively trapped and removed from the cathode region, preventing their interaction with the cathode material and degradation of its electrochemical activity.

Furthermore, the diffusivity of the gaseous contaminant influences the overall kinetics of the adsorption process. A higher diffusivity allows for faster migration of the contaminant molecules to the active sites on the getter material's surface. This results in

enhanced adsorption efficiency and a more rapid removal of contaminants from the system, which is crucial for maintaining the performance and longevity of SOFCs.

Controlling and optimizing the diffusivity of gaseous contaminants can be achieved through several approaches. Firstly, the choice of getter material itself can influence the diffusivity of the contaminants. Getter materials with a highly porous structure and interconnected pore network can promote rapid diffusion and capture of contaminants. Additionally, the design of the getter system, including the geometry and arrangement of the getter material, can also impact the diffusivity by influencing the path and flow of the contaminants within the system.

Computational modeling and simulation techniques have been employed to analyze and predict the diffusivity of gaseous contaminants in SOFCs. These simulations allow for the evaluation of different getter materials, system designs, and operating conditions to optimize the diffusivity and enhance the performance of the getter in capturing and removing contaminants.

In summary, diffusivity plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of getters in SOFCs for capturing and removing gaseous contaminants. The diffusivity of the contaminants directly influences their transport, penetration, and kinetics of adsorption within the getter material. Optimizing the diffusivity is essential for achieving efficient contaminant capture, maintaining the electrochemical activity of the cathode, and prolonging the lifespan of SOFCs. By carefully selecting getter materials, designing effective getter systems, and utilizing computational modeling, researchers can enhance the diffusivity and improve the overall performance of getters in SOFCs, contributing to the advancement of clean and sustainable energy technologies.

Table 4.5 Change in Diffusivity with time in SNO

Flow time (hours)	Maximum Diffusivity reached in channel length (mm)
28	14
56	18

Flow time (hours)	Maximum Diffusivity reached in channel length (mm)
76	22
200	31
300	36
400	43
500	48

Figure 4.5 Change in diffusivity of getter with time in SNO

The above figure has a very similar trend to the porosity graph. That is because the reason behind their behavior is the same. The diffusivity of Sulfur decreases with time due to formation of dense solid products in the pores in the getter. Lower porosity decreases transport of Sulfur to the reaction sites and hence the decreases in Sulfur diffusivity. So, getter needs to be highly porous for higher utilization of getter.

4.6 SMO getter for 1 kW SOFC

Some of the results generated from simulation for SMO getter is explained using tables 4.6 to 4.9 and figures 4.6 to 4.9. The inlet concentration is $1.071 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol/m}^3$. Air flow rate 4 SLPM and temperature 850°C . Coating thickness $10 \mu\text{m}$ and coating porosity 50%. The following table can be found from figure 4.6 by comprehensive careful observation –

Table 4.6 Sulfur outlet concentration for different flowtimes in SMO

Flowtime (hours)	Sulfur outlet concentration (mol/m^3)
28	1.624×10^{-11}
56	3.487×10^{-11}
76	6.304×10^{-11}
200	9.479×10^{-10}
300	3.342×10^{-9}
400	1.75×10^{-8}
500	5.26×10^{-8}

Figure 4.6 S concentration profile along center of channel of getter

From the above graphs, it is clear that the concentration at outlet is increasing with increasing time. This indicates that the getter is losing capability to remove impurity. Getter outlet concentration has to be less than 10^{-9} mol/m³ for it to be used under accelerated conditions. Under accelerated conditions the getter life is 200 hours. However, accelerated the model has a factor of safety of 263.5. So, in real life conditions, this getter can be used for 52000 hours with a factor of safety equal to 1.

Absorption capacity of SMO getter has been observed from figure 4.7. The results from the simulation have been shown in the following table-

Table 4.7 Sulfur Absorption for various flow time in SMO

Flowtime (hours)	Maxed out Sulfur Capacity (%)	Length up to (mm)
28	-	-
56	70	3.5
76	70	7

Flowtime (hours)	Maxed out Sulfur Capacity (%)	Length up to (mm)
200	70	18
300	70	23
400	70	29
500	70	34

Figure 4.7 Absorbed Sulfur profile in the getter.

The above figures shows the absorbed Sulfur profile in terms of Sulfur capacity (ratio of total sulfur absorbed to maximum sulfur absorption capacity) of the getter. Amount of S captured in the getter increases with time, and S front moves forward before reaching maximum capacity. About 30% of getter remains unused as S front advances. Although absorbed S profile becomes flat at 70% capacity, it keeps absorbing S albeit in a slow rate. Porosity change of getter shall now be examined of SMO. At zero flowtime porosity is 50%. Porosity in a getter refers to the amount of empty space or voids within the material. In the context of getter design, porosity is an important factor to consider because it can

affect the material's ability to absorb or adsorb gases¹ and other impurities from the surrounding environment. Higher porosity can result in a greater surface area for gas absorption, but may also reduce the mechanical strength of the material. Conversely, lower porosity may improve the mechanical strength of the material but reduce its gas absorption capacity. In the optimization of getter design, an appropriate porosity level must be determined to achieve a balance between these competing factors and ensure optimal performance. The porosity of the getter material can be controlled through various processing techniques, such as adjusting sintering temperature and time, and using pore-forming agents. From figure 4.8, the results for porosity change can be found. The summarized result can be shown in the following table-

Table 4.8 Change in Porosity with time in SMO

Flow time (hours)	Maximum porosity reached in channel length (mm)
28	14
56	18
76	22
200	31
300	36
400	43
500	48

Figure 4.8 Change in porosity of getter with time

Figure 4.8 shows the change in average porosity of getter coating with time. The porosity of the getter decreases with time due to formation of dense solid products in the pores. Lower porosity decreases transport of Sulfur to the reaction sites and decreases Sulfur absorption and Sulfur front advances before reaching to the maximum capacity of the getter as shown in the figures. So, getter needs to be highly porous for higher utilization of getter.

Figure 4.8 shows the diffusivity change in sulfur contaminant with time. The diffusivity of air contaminants is an important factor in determining the effectiveness of a getter material in removing them from the surrounding environment. Diffusivity refers to the rate at which a substance can move through a material or medium, and is dependent on factors such as the concentration gradient and temperature. In the context of a getter, a high diffusivity of air contaminants means that they can rapidly penetrate into the

material, increasing the chances of adsorption or absorption onto the getter surface. Conversely, a low diffusivity means that the contaminants may not be able to reach the getter surface efficiently, reducing its effectiveness.

Therefore, the diffusivity of air contaminants should be considered when selecting or designing a getter material, as well as in determining optimal operating conditions. This can be achieved through experimental measurements and modeling of contaminant diffusivity, which can inform the design of the getter material and its placement in the system. Additionally, other factors such as the surface area and porosity of the getter material can also affect its effectiveness in removing contaminants.

The change in diffusivity is shown in figure 4.9. The short summary is given in the form of a table below –

Table 4.9 Change in Sulfur Diffusivity with time in SMO

Flow time (hours)	Maximum Diffusivity reached in channel length (mm)
28	14
56	18
76	22
200	31
300	36
400	43
500	48

Figure 4.9 Change of Sulfur Diffusivity with time

The above figure has a very similar trend to the porosity graph. That is because the reason behind their behavior is the same. The diffusivity of Sulfur decreases with time due to formation of dense solid products in the pores in the getter. Lower porosity decreases transport of Sulfur to the reaction sites and hence the decreases in Sulfur diffusivity. So, getter needs to be highly porous for higher utilization of getter.

4.7 Comparison of SMO and SNO Getter

In figure 4.10 SMO seems to have higher absorption capacity compared to SNO getter. The concentration profile for SMO and SNO is almost same. That is the reason why a graph containing concentration profile of the two getter cases is not shown in a graph together. However, from capacity graph, we can see that SMO getter is more efficient as it has higher

absorption capacity. This can be attributed to SMO having lower molecular dimensions. The SO₂ gaseous particles can collide with smaller SMO better compared to SNO. Since effective collision between reactants are higher for SMO, SMO has better absorption profile.

Figure 4.10 Absorbed Sulfur Profile in SMO and SNO Getter.

SMO has 6 percent higher capacity compared to SNO if all other operating conditions and inputs are identical. Also, from literature we know that SMO is more thermally and hydrolytically stable at high operating temperature conditions compared to SNO.

Also, to be noted is the fact that product Mn₂O₃ helps in capturing slightly more trace airborne contaminant.

Table 4.10 Comparison of porosity graphs

Flow time (hours)	Maximum porosity reached in channel length (mm) in SMO	Maximum porosity reached in channel length (mm) in SNO
28	14	18
56	18	20
76	22	23
200	31	33
300	36	41
400	43	50
500	48	50

From the above table it is clear that the porosity is decreasing faster in SNO in comparison to SMO. This is because the dense solid formed in SNO has higher molecular volume compared to that in SMO.

Table 4.11 Comparison of diffusivity graphs

Flow time (hours)	Maximum Diffusivity reached in channel length (mm) in SMO	Maximum Diffusivity reached in channel length (mm) in SNO
28	14	18
56	18	20
76	22	23
200	31	33
300	36	41
400	43	50
500	48	50

From the above table it is clear that the diffusivity is decreasing faster in SNO in comparison to SMO. This is because the dense solid formed in SNO has higher molecular volume compared to that in SMO.

From the above observations, it is clear that SMO is certainly better than SNO.

4.8 Comparison of Chromium and Sulfur as Trace Contaminant

Let us look at two graphs. Our two separate cases here are:

- Chromium accelerated on a SNO getter (5)
- Sulfur accelerated on another new SNO getter

In figure 4.36 for both sulfur and chromium cases, the inlet concentration is 1.071×10^{-5} mol/m³. Air flow rate 4 SLPM and temperature 850°C. Coating thickness 10 μm and coating porosity 50% and flowtime 500 hours.

Figure 4.11 Chromium concentration along center of channel in SNO and Sulfur concentration along center of channel in SNO.

Outlet concentration in Cr and S case respectively are 1.546×10^{-7} and 5.288×10^{-8} mol/m³. So, same getter captures more Sulfur compared to Cr if all other conditions are similar. This may be attributed to the higher gas phase contaminant diffusivity of S compared to Cr.

Figure 4.12 Absorbed contaminant profile of SNO getter for S and Cr separately

When SNO is capturing S, it works at a higher capacity (64%) compared to Chromium cases (60%). This may be due to lower product volume of SrSO₄ (46.38) compared to that of SrCrO₄ (52.2 cm³/mol).

4.9 Getter Useful Life

1-hour SO₂ Design Value Trends Since 1990

Figure 4.13 1-hour SO₂ Design Value Trends Since 1990(17)

Accelerated modeling has been used in this computational modeling of SMO and SNO getter. Accelerated modeling, in the context of computer simulations using ANSYS Fluent, refers to the technique of simulating and predicting the behavior of a system or process at an accelerated rate compared to real-time or normal operating conditions. It involves manipulating the simulation parameters to expedite the simulation time while still capturing the essential phenomena and obtaining meaningful results.

Accelerated modeling holds significant importance in various fields of engineering and scientific research. It allows researchers and engineers to gain insights into the long-term behavior, performance, and durability of systems and processes within a shorter timeframe. By compressing time scales, accelerated modeling provides a cost-effective and efficient means of studying and analyzing complex phenomena that would otherwise

require impractical or unfeasible amounts of time for traditional real-time testing or simulations.

In the context of ANSYS Fluent, accelerated modeling is particularly valuable for studying the performance and behavior of systems over extended periods, such as the lifetime of a Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) or other energy systems. These systems often operate for several thousands of hours or more, and conducting real-time experiments or simulations for such durations would be time-consuming and resource-intensive.

By employing accelerated modeling techniques, researchers can simulate the long-term behavior of systems within a fraction of the time it would take in reality. This allows for efficient optimization of system design, evaluation of different operating conditions, and prediction of system performance over extended periods. It enables engineers to make informed decisions, identify potential issues, and improve the overall reliability and efficiency of systems before their deployment.

Accelerated modeling is particularly valuable in assessing the durability and lifetime of materials, components, and devices. It enables researchers to study the degradation mechanisms, wear patterns, and failure modes that occur over extended periods and under different operating conditions. This information is crucial for designing and developing materials with enhanced durability, optimizing maintenance schedules, and predicting the overall lifespan of systems.

Moreover, accelerated modeling facilitates rapid design iterations and sensitivity analysis, allowing researchers to explore a wide range of system configurations and operating parameters. By quickly simulating and evaluating different scenarios, engineers can identify optimal designs, troubleshoot potential issues, and accelerate the development of innovative solutions.

However, it is important to note that accelerated modeling is not a substitute for real-time testing or simulations under actual operating conditions. While it provides valuable insights into long-term behavior, it may not capture all the intricacies and nuances of real-time phenomena. Therefore, it is crucial to validate and verify the results obtained

from accelerated modeling through comparison with experimental data or more detailed simulations.

In summary, accelerated modeling in computer simulations, such as ANSYS Fluent, offers significant advantages for studying and predicting the long-term behavior and performance of systems and processes. By compressing time scales, it enables efficient optimization of system design, assessment of durability and lifetime, rapid design iterations, and sensitivity analysis. Accelerated modeling plays a vital role in reducing costs, saving time, and improving the reliability and efficiency of systems across various fields of engineering and scientific research.

Inlet concentration of SO₂ has been taken 1.071×10^{-5} mol/m³. This is 527 ppb. The revised primary SO₂ standard is at a level of 75 parts per billion (ppb) in 1990. That design value is changing and becoming lesser each year. From figure 4.13, it can be seen that in most cases it is 2 ppb SO₂. Now if we use the accelerated model practically, we would be having a factor of safety about

263.5. But for real practical scenario we have to use factor of safety to be 1.

The concentration of sulfur at the end of the length of getter to be equal or less than 10^{-9} mol/m³ or 0.05 ppb in accelerated case. From SMO concentration graph, getter useful life would be 200 hours in accelerated conditions. Then the useful life of the getter would be 200 times 263.5 or 52000 hours. A SOFC plant has a lifetime of 400000 hours to 50000 hours. So, 1 getter needed per SOFC plant.

Chapter 5

5 Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

In order to optimize the design of a Sulfur (S) getter for use in a 1 kW Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) system, a transient, two-dimensional computational model was developed. The aim of this study was to investigate the behavior of the getter material under varying conditions, including changes in flowtime and exposure to airborne contaminants. Two different getter materials, Strontium Manganese Oxide (SMO) and Strontium Nickel Oxide (SNO), were compared using comprehensive computational simulations. The results of this study indicated that SMO was the superior getter material for use in the SOFC system.

Furthermore, the interaction between chromium and the getter material, as well as the interaction between sulfur and the getter material, were investigated numerically. These computational simulations showed that the life of the getter material was primarily dependent on the dosage of sulfur present, rather than the concentration of other airborne trace contaminants.

The accelerated modeling results revealed that the SMO getter material could last up to 50,000 hours for airborne sulfur dioxide (SO₂), which is equivalent to the entire lifetime of the SOFC plant, provided that the concentration of SO₂ in the air remains at 2 parts per billion (ppb) or less. This research highlights the potential of computational modeling and simulation techniques to inform the design and optimization of getter materials for use in high-temperature electrochemical devices such as SOFCs.

5.2 Recommendation

Getter computational modeling can be done for sulfur contaminant for multiple concentration cases. Getter computational modeling can also be done for multiple contaminants at the same time. Computational modelling can be done for simultaneous SO₂ and Cr exposure.

References

- [1] The Canadian Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Association. "Fuel Cell-The Sustainable Hydrogen Power Source." chfca.ca. <https://www.chfca.ca/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/CHFCA-Infographic-01.png> (accessed May 7,2022)
- [2] Department of Energy, "Appendix A Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Primer." energy.gov. <https://www.energy.gov/fecm/articles/appendix-sofc-primer> (accessed May 7,2022)
- [3] Yoshima Ando, Hiroyuki Oozawa, Mashairo Mihara, Hiroki Irie, Yasutaka Urashita, Takuo Ikegami, Mitsubishi Heavy Industries Technical Review Vol. 52 No. 4 , 2015
- [4] Nigel P. Brandon, Enrique Ruiz-Trejo and Paul Boldrin, Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Lifetime and Reliability, USA, Elsevier, 2017
- [5] M.A. Uddin, C. Banas, Chiying Liang, U. Pasaogullari, K. Recknagle, B. Koeppel, J. Stevenson, P. Singh, Design and Optimization of Chromium Getter for SOFC Systems through Computational Modeling ,1-8,2017, doi 10.1149/07801.1063
- [6] Junsung Hong, Ashish Aphale, Su Jeong Heo, Boxun Hu, Michael Reiser, Serphim Belko, P. Singh, Strontium Manganese Oxide Getter for Capturing Airborne Cr and S Contaminants in High-Temperature Electrochemical Systems, 1-8,2019, doi: 10.1021/acsami.9b09677
- [7] C. Lianga, B. Hua, A. N. Aphalea, M. B. Venkataraman, M. K. Mahapatra, and P. Singh, ECS Trans., 75, 57 ,2017
- [8] P. Singh, Materials and Approaches for the Mitigation of SOFC Cathode Degradation in SOFC Power Systems, Pittsburgh, PA, 2016
- [9] S. P. Murarka and R. A. Swalin, J. Phy. Chem. Solids, 32, 1971
- [10] Birney R. Fish, Jack L. Durham, Diffusion Coefficient of SO₂ in air, 2-7, 1971
- [11] IIT."SMO MSDS". cen.itb.ac.in . https://cen.itb.ac.in 22_msds.pdf
- [12] [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Manganese\(III\)_oxide](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Manganese(III)_oxide)
- [13] <https://materialsproject.org/materials/mp-1017466/>
- [14] J. Young and B. A. Pint, Oxidation Metals, 66, 137, 2006
- [15] Aqua Calculator, <https://www.aqua-calc.com/calculate/mole-to-volume-andweight/substance/strontium-blank-sulfate>
- [16] Ansys Inc, Ansys Fluent UDF Manual, USA, ANSYS, 2013

- [17] Environmental Protection Agency."Air quality design value".portal.ct.gov.
https://portal.ct.gov/-/media/DEEP/air_monitoring/trends/1hrSO2DVsPDF.pdf 65
(accessed Jan. 4,2023)
- [18] Mori, N.; Sato, Y.; Iha, M.; Takada, T.; Konoike, T.; Kishimoto, H.; Yamaji, K.;
Yokokawa, H. Sulfur Poisoning of LSCF Cathode in Single Step Co-Fired SOFC.
ECS Trans., 68, 1015– 1022, 2015
- [19] Singh, P.; Birks, N. Reaction of Cobalt in Ar-SO₂ Atmospheres at 500–900 °C.
Oxid. Met. 12, 23–34. 1978
- [20] Zhen, Y.; Tok, A. I. Y.; Boey, F. Y. C.; Jiang, S. P. Development of Cr-Tolerant
Cathodes of Solid Oxide Fuel Cells. Electrochem. Solid-State Lett. 2008, 11,
B42–B46 [21] Chen, Y.; Zhou, W.; Ding, D.; Liu, M.; Ciucci, F.; Tade, M.; Shao,
Z. Advances in Cathode Materials for Solid Oxide Fuel Cells: Complex Oxides
without Alkaline Earth Metal Elements. Adv. Energy Mate.,(1–34), 2015
- [22] Alloy for SOFC Interconnects ZMG TM 232G10 with Improved Oxidation
Resistance and Electrical Conductivity,
https://www.hitachimetals.co.jp/e/products/infr/en/pdf/zmg232-1_g10r_e.pdf
(accessed August 3, 2019).
- [23] Zhang, H. H.; Zeng, C. L. Preparation and Performances of Co-Mn Spinel
Coating on a Ferritic Stainless Steel Interconnect Material for Solid Oxide Fuel
Cell Application. J. Power Sources, 252, 122–129. 2014
- [24] Stodolny, M. K.; Boukamp, B. A.; Blank, D. H. A.; van Berkel, F. P. F.
CrPoisoning of a LaNi_{0.6}Fe_{0.4}O₃ Cathode under Current Load. J. Power Sources
,209, 120–129, 2012
- [25] Mah, J. C. W.; Muchtar, A.; Somalu, M. R.; Ghazali, M. J. Metallic Interconnects
for Solid Oxide Fuel Cell: A Review on Protective Coating and Deposition
Techniques. Int. J. Hydrogen Energy, 42, 9219–9229, 2017
- [26] Junsung Hong , M. R. Anisur, Su Jeong Heo , Pawan Kumar Dubey and
Prabhakar Singh, Sulfur Poisoning and Performance recovery of SOFC Air
Electrodes.
- [27] Prabhakar Singh, Development of Chromium and Sulfur Getter for SOFC
Systems, 2018